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A Review of Dr. Waghe's Textbook of Roga Nidana and Vikruti Vigyana Paper-2.

Dr. Pallavi U. Chougule¹, Dr. Uday V. Chougule²

¹Associate Professor and HOD, Dept. of Rognidan and Vikruti Vigyan, Aarihant Ayurvedic Medical College & Research Institute, Gandhinagar, Gujarat- 382420, India

²Associate Professor, Dept. of Ras Shastra and Bhasajya Kalpana, Aarihant Ayurvedic Medical College & Research Institute, Gandhinagar, Gujarat- 382420, India

Corresponding author: Dr. Pallavi U. Chougule

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Title: - Dr. Waghe's Textbook of *Roga Nidana* and *Vikruti Vigyana* – Paper-2, By Prof. Dr. Subhash D. Waghe, Rashttra Gaurav Publication, Nagpur, 1st edition, 2019, ISBN: 978- 81-939098-1-2

Introduction:

In the realm of *Ayurveda*, the ancient science of holistic healing, the understanding of disease pathology is fundamental and intricately intertwined with concepts of wellness, balance, and harmony. "Dr. Waghe's Textbook of *Roga Nidana* and *Vikruti Vigyana*- Paper 2" emerges as a beacon, illuminating the path towards comprehending the essence of disease and diagnosis within the framework of *Ayurveda* principles of *Nidan panchak* and serves as the backbone of medical education, offering insights into the processes that lead to illness and guiding effective diagnosis. Among the plethora of textbooks available in this domain, "Dr. Waghe's Textbook of *Roga Nidana* and *Vikruti Vigyana*- Paper 2" stands out as a comprehensive guide for students and professionals alike.

Synopsis:

Authored by renowned expert in the field, Dr. Subhash D. Waghe, "Dr. Waghe's Textbook of

Roga Nidana and *Vikruti Vigyana*- Paper 2" delves deep into the mechanisms underlying various diseases, providing a clear and concise overview of essential concepts. The book is a scholarly exposition of the principles of *Nidan* in *Ayurveda*. Each chapter is structured in a student-friendly format, meticulously elucidating the definition, general and specific causes, general and specific pathology, manifestations, complications, prognosis and diagnostic methods pertaining to various diseases.

Through a synthesis of classical *Ayurveda* texts and contemporary research, the author unravels the intricate tapestry of disease etiology and pathophysiology with remarks to understand from modern point of view, paving the way for a holistic approach to health and healing. Appropriate research findings have been added as per necessity and relevance for additional knowledge update to student's quest.

Key Features:

1. Comprehensive Coverage: Written in accordance with the NCISM syllabus the book encompasses a broad spectrum of diseases, ranging from various *srotodusti janya vyadhis*, *upasarg vyadhis*, *krimi*

vigyan ensuring a deeper understanding of the concepts.

2. **Classical Foundation:** Drawing from ancient *Ayurveda* texts such as *asbruhatrayees*, *laghutrayees*, *Kashyap Samhita*, *Harit Samhita*, *Bhel Samhita*,
3. *Siddhant Nidana* and many more the book provides a solid grounding in the foundational principles of Ayurveda Diagnosis.
4. **Practical Relevance:** The authors adeptly bridge the gap between classical wisdom and modern applications, offering insights into the relevance of Ayurveda diagnostics in the context of contemporary science researches and scientific evidences. For ex.
 - a. For the first time *Sapta Kushtha* are brought out as advance stage of one and same entity with evidence from the classics.
 - b. The ancient classification of *Krumis* (microbes) based on their colour, size & shape, habitat, disease produced etc reminds us the the modern style of classification. The correlation of Ayurvedic *krumis* with modern microbes is very rational and evidence based.
 - c. *Visarpa* is rightly correlated with acute necrotizing skin infection
 - d. The modern plummer vinson syndrome is very well traced with regard to complication of disease *Pandu*.
 - e. Author has proved that Koylonchia feature in *Pandu* was first mentioned in Ayurveda with evidence and many more such explorations have been incorporated in the book.
5. **Pictorial Presentations:** Real-life case study photographs, X-ray photographs and clinical correlations enrich the narrative, illustrating the application of Ayurveda principles in diagnosing clinical conditions.
6. **Illustrative Visuals:** Richly illustrated diagrams and tables enhance understanding, facilitating visual learners in grasping intricate concepts and memorizing effectively.
7. **Integration of Research:** Incorporation of the latest research findings ensures that readers stay abreast of advancements in the field, fostering a culture of evidence-based practice.
8. **Clarity and Accessibility:** Complex concepts are well compiled and elucidated with clarity, making them easily comprehensible even for readers with limited prior knowledge in the field.
9. **Scholarly Discourse:** Written in a scholarly yet accessible manner, the book caters to a diverse audience, including undergraduate students, post graduate students, practitioners, and researchers seeking to deepen their understanding of Ayurveda pathology.
10. **Clinical Relevance:** Emphasis is placed on the clinical relevance of pathophysiological mechanisms, modern diagnostic parameters like laboratory investigations, imaging techniques, bridging the gap between basic science and clinical practice.

Review:

"Dr. Waghe's Textbook of *Roga Nidana* and *Vikruti Vigyana*- Paper 2" transcends the confines of a conventional textbook, serving as a scholarly treatise that enriches the reader's intellectual journey into the realms of Ayurveda medicine. The authors' erudition and mastery of the subject shine through, as they adeptly navigate through the intricacies of disease etiology with clarity and precision. What sets this book apart is its seamless integration of classical wisdom with contemporary perspectives, fostering a nuanced understanding of disease pathology. One of the book's notable strengths lies in its ability to strike a balance between depth and accessibility. While delving into intricate

pathophysiological mechanisms, it maintains a conversational tone, engaging readers without overwhelming them with extensive data. Moreover, the book's emphasis on practical relevance and latest research advances makes it a valuable resource for both aspiring Ayurveda practitioners and seasoned healthcare professionals seeking to broaden their horizons.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, " Dr. Waghe's Textbook of *Roga Nidana* and *Vikruti Vigyana*- Paper 2" stands as a testament to the timeless wisdom of Ayurveda, offering a profound exploration of disease pathology within the framework of holistic healing. Whether you're a student embarking on your journey into Ayurveda medicine or a seasoned practitioner seeking to deepen your understanding, this book is sure to enrich your knowledge and transform your approach to Ayurveda diagnosis.

Rating: 5/5

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Dr. Pallavi U. Chougule Inter. J.Digno. and Research

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